

РАЗДЕЛ. ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫЕ НАУКИ

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**ANALYSIS OF RISK FACTORS, CLINICAL OUTCOMES
AND MORTALITY IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19**

A.S. Aleksandrovich,

Ph.D., Associate Professor

T.I. Zimatkina,

Ph.D., Associate Professor

T.I. Vitko,

S.V. Kojemiakin,

Grodno state medical university,

Grodno

Annotation: The course of COVID-19 was analyzed and the main risk factors in various population groups were identified., a link was made between symptoms such as fever, shortness of breath, weakness, chills, fatigue, dry cough, anorexia, anosmia, ageusia, dizziness and sweating and COVID-19. The study revealed a direct correlation between the more severe course of the disease, age, and abnormal levels of C-reactive protein in patients with COVID-19.

Keywords: COVID-19, risk factors, symptoms

**АНАЛИЗ ФАКТОРОВ РИСКА, КЛИНИЧЕСКИХ ИСХОДОВ
И СМЕРТНОСТИ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С COVID-19**

А.С. Александрович,

к.м.н., доц.

Т.И. Зиматкина,

к.б.н., доц.

**Т.И. Витко,
С.В. Кожемякин,**

Гродненский государственный медицинский университет,
г. Гродно

Аннотация: Проанализировано течение COVID-19 и выявлены основные факторы риска у различных групп населения., проведена связь между такими симптомами, как лихорадка, одышка, слабость, озноб, усталость, сухой кашель, анорексия, аносмия, агевзия, головокружение и потливость и COVID-19. В процессе исследования выявлена прямая корреляция между более тяжелым течением болезни, возрастом, аномальным уровнем С-реактивного белка у пациентов с COVID-19.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, факторы риска, симптомы

Relevance. In December 2019, a group of patients fell ill with an acute respiratory disease of unknown etiology. Subsequently, a coronavirus was detected in the sick, which previously caused severe acute respiratory syndrome in infected people. The virus turned out to be very contagious, causing fatigue, cough, fever and moderate to severe respiratory failure. Some patients developed acute respiratory failure, septic shock and complications such as acute respiratory distress syndrome and multiple organ dysfunction syndrome rather quickly, which subsequently led to the death of patients [1].

In elderly people with concomitant diseases, such as acute kidney disease, diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular diseases, cancer and hypertension, the risk of death was especially high. Subsequently, an unexpectedly high mortality rate was recorded, the frequency of which increased with age and especially in the presence of concomitant diseases listed above in patients [2].

When comparing the clinical symptoms in elderly patients with COVID-19 with patients of middle and young age, it turned out that all had such common symptoms as fever, sputum and cough. The percentage of involvement of several lobes of the lung and the index of severity of pneumonia were significantly higher in the group of elderly patients compared with those in the middle and young age group [1].

Further, the clinical and epidemiological characteristics of the coronavirus were investigated using data from radiological, laboratory, clinical, demographic and epidemiological research methods in 99 patients with confirmed COVID-19. Common symptoms in all patients were fever, fatigue and dry cough. The average age of patients was 49 years, 41 % had coronavirus without confirmed contact, 49 % had confirmed contacts with patients infected with COVID-19. Early symptoms in seriously ill patients were: a decrease in the number of leukocytes, lymphocytes and neutrophils; higher levels of brain sodium-uretic peptide; higher levels of C-reactive protein [1].

Subsequently, the features associated with liver damage associated with COVID-19 were studied. The study included 75 male and 73 female patients with an average age of 50 years. It was found that elevated levels of total bilirubin, alkaline phosphatase, gamma-glutamyltransferase and aspartate and alanine aminotransferase are considered markers of liver dysfunction in COVID-19. It was proved that patients with impaired liver function required longer inpatient treatment than patients with unchanged liver function [2].

Patients with heart transplantation may have a higher risk of death from COVID-19 due to clinically significant immunosuppression and a number of other concomitant diseases. Clinical manifestations, treatment, and outcomes in patients with COVID-19 with arterial hypertension were studied. A 25 % mortality rate was recorded in patients with arterial hypertension suffering from COVID-19 infection [3].

After studying the clinical symptoms and outcomes in patients infected with COVID-19 who died or suffered acute respiratory distress syndrome, risk factors such as blood clotting disorders, neutrophilia and old age were identified, which are directly related to the development of acute respiratory distress syndrome and death. The researchers concluded that due to a reduced immune response, elderly patients have a higher risk of developing acute respiratory distress syndrome and death [1].

The study of other risk factors is relevant.

Goal. To analyze the course of COVID-19 and identify the main risk factors in various population groups. To make a connection between symptoms such as fever, shortness of breath, weakness, chills, fatigue, dry cough, anorexia, anosmia, ageusia, dizziness and sweating and COVID-19.

Research methods. The Pubmed database of scientific publications was used to search for materials. 44 scientific publications on the topic for 2019-2022 were selected. Statistical processing of the received data was performed on a personal computer using a set of standard statistical programs.

Results and their discussion. The results of examinations of 319 patients (mean age 45.48 ± 18.50 years, 142 men and 177 women) with flu-like symptoms during the COVID-19 pandemic were selected for analysis. All clinical data were examined, including anamnesis, epidemiology and medical history, symptoms, signs, epidemiological and clinical data of patients. Patients with flu-like symptoms underwent computed tomography of the lungs as a non-invasive test to assess the condition of the lungs, as well as high-resolution thin-layer multilayer spiral computed tomography [3].

Of the patients with COVID-19, one had leukemia, one had a progressive form of thyroid cancer and one had bone marrow cancer. These patients with leukemia and bone marrow cancer died. During the illness, two patients had a stroke, with a positive outcome in one person. One patient with a history of tuberculosis died. Two patients had renal failure, both of them died [4].

Data analysis showed a significant difference in healthy people and patients with COVID-19 in terms of the severity of symptoms such as fever, shortness of breath, weakness, trembling, fatigue and dry cough. Symptoms such as anorexia, anosmia, ageusia, dizziness and sweating also differed significantly in healthy and COVID-19 patients. All of the above symptoms were more pronounced in patients with COVID-19, compared to healthy [5].

When considering symptoms such as chest pain, sore throat and cough with sputum, there was no significant difference between healthy and COVID-19 patients. The pathological level of C-reactive protein was significantly higher in patients with COVID-19, compared with healthy [4].

It was found that the occurrence of O–blood group in patients with COVID-19 is lower than in healthy people. There was no significant difference between healthy and COVID-19 carriers of AB–, A–, A+, B+, AB+, B– and O+ blood groups. The presence or absence of BCG vaccination did not show any significant difference between patients with COVID-19 and healthy people. There were also no significant differences

between healthy and sick COVID-19 with respect to diabetes mellitus, immunodeficiency, hematological diseases, rheumatological diseases, corticosteroid therapy, tobacco use, and gender. There was no significant difference between healthy and sick COVID-19 infection with respect to asthma, liver disease, cancer, heart disease, kidney disease and organ transplantation [5].

The greatest risk of COVID-19 infection was found in people aged 25 to 55 years. They are an active workforce of society and have a higher level of interaction with each other. It was noticed that the groups with negative blood rhesus were infected much less often than the groups with positive blood rhesus. In the presence of positive blood groups O+, A+, B+ and AB+, patients are more susceptible to infection.

There was a significant directly proportional relationship between old age, the presence of cardiovascular diseases, the presence of cancer and mortality from COVID-19. Representatives of the O+ blood group showed a decrease in mortality from COVID-19 compared to patients with other blood groups. In the presence of symptoms such as anosmia, dry cough, ageusia, fever and anorexia, mortality from COVID-19 was higher than in patients with their absence.

When studying mortality in infected people aged 25 to 55 years, the mortality rate among them was the lowest. There was no mortality in patients aged 40 to 60 years. The data obtained did not mean that young people are completely insured against death. Two cases of coronavirus infection with a fatal outcome were detected at the age of 30 and 40 years. These two deaths had some general similarities: the 30-year-old patient was a woman with diabetes and shortness of breath. A 40-year-old man suffered from lung disease and shortness of breath. No other concomitant diseases were registered in them. With a low level of infection among the elderly, their high mortality was revealed [4].

Conclusions. The study revealed a direct correlation between the more severe course of the disease, age, and abnormal levels of C-reactive protein in patients with COVID-19. It was found that the O–blood group demonstrated a protective effect against COVID-19, however, additional studies are needed to prove this pattern, which is beyond the scope of this study. There was also a direct correlation between old age, a history of cardiovascular and oncological diseases and mortality in patients with COVID-19. The development of symptoms such as anosmia, dry cough,

ageusia, fever and anorexia are also predictors of high mortality from COVID-19. O+ blood type is a protective factor that reduces mortality associated with COVID-19. Fever is one of the most significant symptoms of COVID-19 infection.

Bibliography

[1] The correlation between BCG immunization coverage and the severity of COVID-19 / Y. Li [et al] // Egypt J Bronchol. – 2020. Vol. 14. № 1. 25-43 p.

[2] Dayal D. Connecting BCG vaccination and COVID-19 additional data / D. Dayal, S. Gupta // Medrxiv. – 2020. Vol. 26. № 5. 1-9 p.

[3] Iftime S. Risk factors associated with mortality in hospitalized patients with SARS-CoV-2infection / S. Iftime, AF. López-Azcona, M. Vicente-Miralles // BioRxiv. – 2020. Vol. 9. № 2. 1-28 p.

[4] Sun H. Risk factors for mortality in 244 older adults with COVID-19 / H. Sun, R. Ning, Y. Tao // J Am Geriatr Soc. – 2020. Vol. 68. № 6. 19-23 p.

[5] Chen R. Risk factors of fatal outcome in hospitalized subjects with coronavirus disease 2019 / R. Chen, W. Liang, M. Jiang // Chest. – 2020. Vol. 158. № 7. 97-105 p.

Список литературы

[1] Корреляция между охватом иммунизацией БЦЖ и тяжестью COVID-19 / Y. Li [et al] // Egypt J Bronchol. – 2020. Том. 14. № 1. 25-43 с.

[2] Dayal D. Связь вакцинации БЦЖ и дополнительных данных о COVID-19 / D. Dayal, S. Gupta // Medrxiv. – 2020. Том. 26. № 5. 1-9 p.

[3] Iftime S. Факторы риска, связанные со смертностью у госпитализированных пациентов с инфекцией SARS-CoV-2 / S. Iftime, AF. Лопес-Аскона, М. Висенте-Миральес // BioRxiv. – 2020. Том. 9. № 2. 1-28 p.

[4] Sun H. Факторы риска смертности у 244 пожилых людей с COVID-19 / H. Sun, R. Ning, Y. Tao // J Am Geriatr Soc. – 2020. Том. 68. № 6. 19-23 с.

[5] Чен Р. Факторы риска летального исхода у госпитализированных с коронавирусной болезнью 2019 г. / Р. Чен, В. Лян, М. Цзян // Грудь. – 2020. Том. 158. № 7. 97-105 с.

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